

Conversational Implicature in the *Webtoon* Suddenly, I Became a Princess

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ABSTRACT: In conversation events, sometimes the speech contains a specific purpose that is different from what is said. This condition is done by someone to disguise his speech. This research discussed the conversational implicature contained in a webtoon. The aims of this research 1) to describe the conversational implicatures and intentions contained in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess, and 2) to analyse the conversational implicatures and intentions contained in the webtoon. This research used qualitative descriptive methods. The data collection technique used the listening technique with advanced techniques in the form of note-taking techniques by collecting data in the form of conversational sentences between characters from episodes 21-41 which contain conversational implicatures. The data were analyzed by classifying conversational implicature using three types of conversational implicature (Yule, 2014) which are divided into general conversational implicature, special conversational implicature, and scaled conversational implicature. The results of the analysis, there were 42 utterances which contain conversational implicature, 17 utterances of general conversational implicature, furthermore 20 utterances of special conversational implicature, and 5 utterances of scaled conversational implicature.

KEYWORDS: Conversational Implicature, Implicature, Pragmatics, Webtoon.

INTRODUCTION

Conversations between speakers and interlocutors contain a certain meaning or purpose. This condition is done by someone to hide his speech which allows the realization of politeness in language events. Each speaker has his own way in conveying a speech to the interlocutor which sometimes the meaning of the speech has a direct or indirect meaning. In this case, the speaker fulfills the rules of conversation, so that the meaning and speech can be understood by the interlocutor. If the utterance has an indirect or implied meaning, this causes misunderstandings in communication because the interlocutor does not understand the message intended by the speaker in the spoken utterance, there is a misunderstanding of the meaning. This is called conversational implicature in pragmatic studies.

Some of the implied or implicit meanings of a speech are not only found in everyday conversations, but also could be found in several conversations contained in audiovisuals, works of fiction, and others such as dramas, films, novels, magazines or comics. As technology advances, social media is not only used to communicate. Today's social media allows creating, editing, and sharing with others, using relatively simple and easy-to-use tools. Digital comics are one of the results of technological changes which were originally through print media, now they can be enjoyed in digital form.

Digital comics were originally formed from a book that was scanned and converted into digital form illegally because information technology had developed (Leech, in Lestari & Iswansyah, 2020:136; Amir p et al., 2022). Webtoon is a compound word that comes from the word web which means internet, and the word toon which means cartoon. Digital comics are digitally published comics, consisting of one image or composed of several parts, with a plot, frames and speech bubbles, and a writing style with visual meaning. (Aggleton, in Lestari & Iswansyah, 2020: 135; Abbas et al., 2022).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Based on the background described previously, this research aims 1) to describe conversational implications are contained in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess, and 3) to analyze the meaning of the conversational implicature contained in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pragmatics is closely related to the conditions that use of language in communication incompatible or not. Harmony is needed in conveying the meaning of speech, it used as good communication between the speaker and interlocutor. So far, linguistic studies examines language without paying attention to aspects of its use, or in other words who used it. Meanwhile, with pragmatics, language is studied based on its used or how language is used in social life. In this case Levinson (1983:9) argued that pragmatics is the study of the relationships between language and context that are grammaticalized and encoded in the structure of a language. According to Levinson (1983: 10) state that pragmatics is a study that discusses aspects of the relationship between language and context based on the explanation of the language, this means to understand the use of language, we are also required to understand the context that embodies the use of the language.

Morris, (in Putrayasa, 2014:14) was the first to introduce the term pragmatics, in this case Morris divided semiotics into three namely syntax, semantics, and pragmatics. Based on this division, pragmatics is generally stated as meaning in use or meaning in context. So, the meaning of the speakers and those who listen to it must be in accordance with the narrative and context. In this case, Parker (in Putrayasa, 2014: 14) stated that pragmatics is the study of the use of language to pay attention to the intention in the act of speaking based on the context and situation of the conversation. The participation of the context in the narration of meaning is what distinguishes semantics and pragmatics. Semantics is the study of context-independent meaning, while it is the study of context-bound meaning (Andini et al., 2022).

Leech (1993:8) mentioned that pragmatics is the study of the meaning of statements in relation to certain situations. Pragmatics examined what is said, although sometimes something said is not in line with its meaning. So, in interpreting an utterance, what needs to be considered is not only the meaning of the utterance uttered, but also must pay attention to the situation, the speaker, and the utterance. Leech also pointed out that the nature of language cannot be understood unless pragmatics is understood, and as it deals with how language is used in the narrative of communication that occurs in society.

Leech (in Putrayasa, 2014: 94) explained that context is the background of understanding that is owned by the speaker and also the interlocutor, which causes the interlocutor to make interpretations about what the speaker means when the utterance occurs. It helps the interlocutor interpret the intent of the speaker. Leech also stated (in Niatri, 2016: 28) that he considers context as any prior knowledge that must be shared between the speaker and the listener and it helps the listener's interpretation of what the speaker hears. Leech considers context to be useful as background knowledge shared by the speaker and the interlocutor in order for the interlocutor to accept the speaker's intention through speech. Thus, the context is the things that hold on to the physical and social environment of an utterance or the background knowledge possessed by the speaker as well as the interlocutor and which helps the interlocutor in interpreting the meaning of the utterance (Anriadi et al., 2022; Hasnia et al., 2022).

Wijana (in Niatri, 2016:42) emphasized that context is important because pragmatics examined meaning tied to context. In line with that Searle et al., (1980) also noted that pragmatics refers to the way in which the interpretation of syntactically defined expressions depends on the specific conditions of their use in the context. Pragmatics is closely related to how to interpret expressions depending on certain conditions of the narrative in context.

Rustono (1999:20), explained that context is something that becomes a means to clarify the intent of a speech. This tool is divided into two kinds, namely in the form of an expression that can support the interpretation of meaning and a situation related to an event. This is in line with the opinion of Cahyono & Widiati, (2015) explained that there are two kinds of context, namely linguistic context and physical context. The linguistic context is the context that influences the interpretation of the meaning of words, while the physical context is the context that relates to the time and place where the narrative occurs. Therefore, the meaning of an utterance cannot be understood if you do not pay attention to the context in which the speaker makes the utterance (Syawal et al., 2022).

When someone makes a speech it is better to follow the rules in the narrative, this means that the speech is easily understood by the interlocutor, but sometimes in situations intentionally or unintentionally sometimes a speaker violates these rules. This result in the existence of something that is implied or something that is implicit in the use of an utterance. Something that is implied or the implicit meaning in the use of this language is called the implicature. Implicature is a study of pragmatics that analyzes the implicit meaning of an utterance.

Grice (1975) argued that implicature is an implicit suggestion or utterance, namely something that speakers may interpret, imply, or mean differently from what is said. This concept is used to describe the difference that sometimes exists between 'what is said' and 'what is meant'.

METHOD

This research used a descriptive qualitative method. Qualitative methods aim to obtain a complete picture of a matter from the point of view of the human being studied (Basuki, 2006:78). This method is to describe, or provide an explanation of the research data as it is, without providing conclusions regarding right-wrong or good-bad to the object under study. The researcher wants to provide an overview of the conversational implicatures contained in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data in this research is in the form of utterances that contain conversational implicatures in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess. According to Yule's theory (2014), as well as the context and intent contained in the implicature of the conversation. Data was collected using the listening and note-taking technique, namely by listening to the speech in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess, then recording it in a data table to classify conversational implicatures. The data studied totaled 20 episodes, from episode 21 to episode 41.

Based on the results of the analysis obtained in this webtoon which totals 20 episodes, 42 sentences were found which conversational implicatures were. The collected data are classified into three categories of conversational implicatures based on Yule's theory (2014), which consist of general conversational implicatures; special conversational implicature; and scaled conversational implicature. The amount of conversational implicature data based on its classification is as follows:

Table 1. Conversational Implicature Classification

No	Conversational Implicature	Amount of data
1	General Conversational Implicature	17
2	Special Conversational Implicature	20
3	Scalable Conversational Implicature	5
Total		42

The results of the analysis are found regarding conversational implicatures which have been classified into three sections will be described in the discussion section. However, due to efficiency, in this research all the results of conversational implicature analysis will not be described. In this case, the selected data is based on differences in its classification function, to explain in detail the results of the conversational implicature analysis. The selected data will be further explained in the table, as follows:

Table 2. General Conversational Implicature

No	Conversational Implicature Data	Eps.	Function
1	A: 저기, 아빠. 아티 혼자 걷고 싶어요... Jeogi, Appa. Athi honja keodgo sipheoyo. Dad. Athi wants to walk alone... B: 이게 더 빠르다. Ige deo ppareuda. It's faster..	21	Refuse
2	A: 폐하, 공주님은 제가 안을까요? Phyeha, gongjunimeun jega aneulkkayo? Yang Your Highness, let me carry the Princess? B: 지금보다 다섯 걸을 뒤에서 따라와라. Jigeumboda daseot geomeul duiseo ttarawara. Follow me five steps back from where I am.	21	Order

3	<p>A: 너 나중에 학자라도 될 생각이야? Neo najunge hakjarado dwel saenggakiya?</p> <p>B: You want to be a scientist, right? 공부를 꼭 학자가 되려고만 하나? Gongbureul kok hakjaka dweryeogoman hana? Do people study just because they want to be scientists?</p>	23	Argue
4	<p>A: 아빠아! 아빠아, 보고 싶었어요오. Appaa! Appaa, bogo sipheoyooo. daddy! Dad, I miss you</p> <p>B: . 정신 사납게 뛰지 마라. 넘어진다. Jeongsin sanabke dweji mara. Neumojinda. Don't run around making me dizzy. You can fall.</p>	24	Forbid
5	<p>A: 물론 마법사님이라 해도 우리 공주님보다는 아니지만요. 우리 공주님은 벌써 6 대 철학서를 다~ Mullon mabeonsanimira haedo uti gongjunimbodaneun anijimanyo. Uri gongjunimeun bolsso 6dae cheolhakseul da~ Of course even though she is a witch, she still can't be compared to the princess. Our Lady has finished all 6 philosophy books ~</p> <p>B: 릴리, 나 졸려. Lili, na jullyeo. Lily, I'm sleepy</p>	27	Divert
6	<p>A: 하지만, 그런 자리나 춤추는 거 별로 안좋아하는거 아니에요? Hajiman, keureon jarina chumcuneun geo byeollo anjoahaneungo aniyeyo? But, isn't it that Father doesn't really like dancing in events like that?</p> <p>B: 기껏해야 춤 한번, 에스코트 한번이 뭐가 그리 대단한 일이라고. Gikkeothaeya chum hambon, eseukotey hamboni mwoga geuri daedanhan irirago. All I need to do is dance once and accompany you once, no big deal.</p>	27	Confirm
7	<p>A: 정말 저랑 같이 데뷔당트 파티에 가 주실 거예요? Jeongmal jeorang kathi debudangte pathie ga jusil goyeyo? You're really going to go to the debutante party with me, right?</p> <p>B: 그렇게까지 원한다는데 하는 수 없지.</p>	27	Agree

	Keurohkekkaji wonhandaneunde haneun su obsji. How can I refuse when you want it to be like that.		
8	A: 알피어스 공자가 제게 그런 청을 하고 싶다면가요? Alphaeus gonjaka jege keuron cheongeul hago sipdadeongayo? Was Lord Alphaeus's son making this request of me? B: 공주님을 보필하는 자리인데 제 아들에게도 당연한 영광이 아니겠습니까. Gongjunimeul bopilhaneun jariinde je adeulegedo dangyeonhan yeongwangin anigeseumnida. That position is to accompany the Princess, of course it will be an honor for my son	28	Report (notify)
9	A: 책 제목이 이게 뭐야? Chaek jemoki ige mwoya? B: What is the title of this book? 이거, 이거 내 거 아니야! C: Igeo, igeo nae kkeo aniya! I, it's not mine! D: 아, 방금 전 흰둥이 아들이 말한 흥미로운 책이라는 게? Ah, banggeum jeon hwendungi adeuli marhan heungmiroun chaekiraneun ge? Ah, so this is the book that was said to be interesting with the white child? 아니야! Aniya! Bukan!	38	Deny
10	A: 너 진짜 성격 나쁜 거 알아? Neo jinjja seonggyok napeun geo ara? Don't you know you're really bad? B: 응, 넌 진짜 바보 같고. 빨리 와. 시간 없어. Eung, Neon Jinjja Babo Kattgo. Ppali Wa. Sigam Obseo. Yes, And You Really Look Like An Idiot. Come On, Quickly. No Time.	40	Mocking

Table 3. Specific Conversational Implicature

No	Conversational Implicature Data	Eps	Function
1.	A: 지난번에 공주님께서도 알피어스의 어린 영식보다 마법사님이 좋다고 하셨지요? Jinanbeone gonjunimkkaesodo Alphaeuseue eorin yeongsikboda mabeobsanimi jottdago hasyeottjiyo?	21	Refuse

	<p>Back then the Princess had also said she preferred the Lord Witch to the son of Lord Alphaeus, right?</p> <p>B: 아티는 새로운 친구 필요 없어! 필릭스만 있으면 된단 말이야!</p> <p>Athineun saeroun chinggu philyo obseo! Felixman isseumyeon dwendan mariya!</p> <p>Athi nggak butuh teman baru! Athi sudah cukup ada Felix!</p>		
2	<p>A: 오빠, 진짜로 몇 살이야?</p> <p>Oppa, jinjjaro myeott sariya?</p> <p>Brother, how old are you actually?</p> <p>B: 그냥 적당히 맛먹어, 어차피 이제부터 같이 늙어 가는 처지에.</p> <p>Geunyang jeokdanghi majmeoko, eocaphi ijebutheo kathi neulgeo ganeun cheojie.</p> <p>Be similar to you. After all, from now on we will grow old together.</p>	21	Report (notify)
3	<p>A: 아빠는?</p> <p>Appaneun?</p> <p>Where's dad?</p> <p>B: 공주님의 까망이는 오늘도 참 귀엽군요. 너무 조그마해서 한 입 거리도 안 되게 생겼네요.</p> <p>Gongjunimeue kkamangineun oneuldo cham kwiyoibgunyo.</p> <p>Neomu jokeumahaeso han ib georido an dweke saengkyeoneyo.</p> <p>The Princess's Black, today is also very sweet. He was so tiny, it didn't even taste like a mouthful.</p>	21	Threaten
4	<p>A: 공주님의 어머니가 무희였던 것이 이럴 때는 도움이 되는군요.</p> <p>Jongjunimeue eomoniha muhwiyetdeon geosi ireol ttenuen doumi dwenuengunyo.</p> <p>It turns out that there are advantages too, that Princess' mother is a dancer.</p> <p>B: 선생님께서 가르쳐 주시는 대로 열심히 배운 것뿐인걸요.</p> <p>seonsaengnimkkeso gareucheo jusineun daero yeolsimhi baeun geotppunilgeolyo.</p> <p>... I only study as taught by the teacher only.</p>	24	Mocking
5	<p>A: 그래서, 지금 나보고 어른 모습으로 변해서 연습 상대를 해달라?</p> <p>Keureso, jigeum nabogo eoreun moseubeuro byeonheso</p>		

	yeonseub sangdaereul haedalla? So, now you're asking me to turn into an adult and be your training opponent? B: 그때 오빠 키가 우리 아빠랑 비슷하지 않았나? Keutte oppa kiga uri apparang biseuthaji anattna? Wasn't the height of my brother and father similar at that time?	25	Agree
6	A: 왜 이렇게 늦게 왔어? Wae ireohke neujke wasso? Kenapa kau datang terlambat sekali? B: 내가 그렇게 한가한 사람인 줄 알아? Naega keurohke hangahan sarami jul ara? You think I have no work?	28	Assert
7	A: 직접 뵈고 나니 소문이 과장이 아닌 걸 알겠더라고요. 그 흰칠하신 모습이라니. Jikjeob bweb nani somuni gwjangi anin geol algetteoraguyo. Keu hwonchilhasil moseubirani. After seeing it in person, it turns out that the news is not exaggerating. Really charming person. B: 아아. 정말 피오레체의 조각상 같은 외모셨죠. Aah, jeongmal phiorecheeue jogaksang katteun wimosyeottjyo. God, his face really looks like a statue of Fiorecce.	36	Hyperbole
8	A: 아까 지나간 사람들이 여기 파르페가 맛있대. Akka jinakan saramdeuri yeogi pareupega massitte. A passer-by said the parfaits here were delicious B: 솔직히 말해봐. 네 위에 경량화 마법 걸려 있지? Soljikhi marhaebwa. Ni wie gyengryanghwa mabeob gelyeo ittji? Honestly say. You used lightening magic, right?	40	Accuse

Table 4. Scaled Conversation Implicature

No	Conversational Implicature Data	Eps.	Function
1	A: 제니트라는 애 말이야. 아까부터 찾고 있었다면서? Zenithraneun ae mariya, akkabutheo chajgo isseosdamyeonseo? Said you're looking for a child named Zenith from earlier? B: 전부 들으셨군요. 실은 혼자 울고 있을 것 같아서 찾기를 망설이고 있었습니다. Jeonbu deureusyeottkunyo. Sireun honja ulgo isseul geott kataseo chajgireul mangseoligo isseosseumnida. You seem to hear everything. Actually, I was scared to look	22	Report

	for him because it looked like he was crying alone.		
2	<p>A: : 제가 곧 이곳을 떠나게 되거든요. 그래서 많이 서운한 것 같아요.</p> <p>Jaega godeu igeoseul tteonaga dwegeodeunyo. Keureseo manhi seounhan geott katayo.</p> <p>Soon I will leave this place. Because of that it seems like he grieves a</p> <p>B lot.흐응~ 오빠를 많이 좋아하나 보네.</p> <p>Heung~ oppareul manhi joahana bone.</p> <p>Hmm.. it seems she really likes her brother.</p>	22	Agree
3	<p>A:그리고 댄스 수업 선생님인요, 제가 춤을 출 때마다 꼭.. 요정을 보는 것 같대요! 헤헤</p> <p>Geurigo dance suob seonsaengniminyo, jaega chumeul chul ttemada kkok... yojeongeul boneun geott kattdeyo! Hehe</p> <p>Then, the dance lesson teacher, every time I dance he always says... he says it's like seeing a fairy! Haha</p> <p>B.풍파듀 부인은 평소에도 헛소리를 자주 하는 편이니 흘러들어라.</p> <p>Pompadour buineun pyeongsoedo heotsorireul jaju haneun pyeonini heulyeodeurora.</p> <p>Madam Pompadour always talks nonsense, don't listen too much.</p>	24	Asking
4	<p>A: 공주님! 이 초대장 좀 보세요!</p> <p>Gonjunim! I chodaejang jom boseyo!</p> <p>Tuan Putri! Lihatlah undangan ini!</p> <p>B: 이게 전부 초대장이야?</p> <p>Ige jeonbu chodaejangiya? Ini all invites?</p> <p>C. 네, 앞으로 더 많아질 거예요.</p> <p>Ne, apeuro deo manhajil geoyeyo.</p> <p>Yes, after this there will be more and more</p>	35	Assert

Table 5. Specific Conversational Implicature

No	Conversational Implicature Data	Eps	Function
11.	<p>A: 지난번에 공주님께서도 알피어스의 어린 영식보다 마법사님이 좋다고 하셨지요?</p> <p>Jinanbeone gonjunimkkaesodo Alphaeuseue eorin yeongsikboda mabeobsanimi jottdago hasyeottjiyo?</p> <p>Back then the Princess had also said she preferred the Lord Witch to the son of Lord Alphaeus, right?</p> <p>B: 아티는 새로운 친구 필요 없어! 필릭스만 있으면 되단</p>	21	Refuse

	<p>말이야! Athineun saeroun chinggu philyo obseo! Felixman isseumyeon dwendan mariya! Athi nggak butuh teman baru! Athi sudah cukup ada Felix!</p>		
12	<p>A: 오빠, 진짜로 몇 살이야? Oppa, jinjjaro myeott sariya? Brother, how old are you actually? B: 그냥 적당히 맛먹어, 어차피 이제부터 같이 늙어 가는 처지에. Geunyang jeokdanghi majmeoko, eocaphi ijebutheo kathi neulgeo ganeun cheojie. Be similar to you. After all, from now on we will grow old together.</p>	21	Report (notify)
13	<p>A: 아빠는? Appaneun? Where's dad? B: 공주님의 까망이는 오늘도 참 귀엽군요. 너무 조그마해서 한 입 거리도 안 되게 생겼네요. Gongjunimeue kkamangineun oneuldo cham kwiyobgunyo. Neomu jokeumahaeso han ib georido an dweke saengkyeoneyo. The Princess's Black, today is also very sweet. He was so tiny, it didn't even taste like a mouthful.</p>	21	Threaten
14	<p>A: 공주님의 어머니가 무희였던 것이 이럴 때는 도움이 되는군요. Jongjunimeue eomoniha muhwiyetdeon geosi ireol ttenuen doumi dwenuengunyo. It turns out that there are advantages too, that Princess' mother is a dancer. B: 선생님께서 가르쳐 주시는 대로 열심히 배운 것뿐인걸요. seonsaengnimkkeso gareuchoe jusineun daero yeolsimhi baeun geotppunilgeolyo. ... I only study as taught by the teacher only.</p>	24	Mocking
15	<p>A: 그래서, 지금 나보고 어른 모습으로 변해서 연습 상대를 해달라? Keureso, jigeum nabogo eoreun moseubeuro byeonheso yeonseub sangdaereul haedalla? So, now you're asking me to turn into an adult and be your training opponent? B: 그때 오빠 키가 우리 아빠랑 비슷하지 않았나?</p>	25	Agree

	Keutte oppa kiga uri apparang biseuthaji anattna? Wasn't the height of my brother and father similar at that time?		
16	A: 왜 이렇게 늦게 왔어? Wae ireohke neujke wasso? Kenapa kau datang terlambat sekali? B:내가 그렇게 한가한 사람인 줄 알아? Naega keurohke hangahan sarami jul ara? You think I have no work?	28	Assert
17	A: 직접 뵈고 나니 소문이 과장이 아닌 걸 알겠더라고요. 그 흰칠하신 모습이라니. Jikjeob bweb nani somuni gwajangi anin geol algettdeoraguyo. Keu hwonchilhasil moseubirani. After seeing it in person, it turns out that the news is not exaggerating. Really charming person. B: 아아. 정말 피오레체의 조각상 같은 외모셨죠. Aah, jeongmal phiorecheeue jogaksang katteun wimosyeottjyo. God, his face really looks like a statue of Fiorecce.	36	Hyperbole
18	A: 아까 지나간 사람들이 여기 파르페가 맛있대. Akka jinakan saramdeuri yeogi pareupega massitte. A passer-by said the parfaits here were delicious B: 솔직히 말해봐. 네 위에 경량화 마법 걸려 있지? Soljikhi marhaebwa. Ni wie gyengryanghwa mabeob gelyeo ittji? Honestly say. You used lightening magic, right?	40	Accuse

The analysis of conversational implicatures in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess found that there were 42 conversational implicature data divided into three classifications namely, 17 general conversational implicature data; 20 custom conversational implicature data; and 5 scaled conversational implicature data. From a total of 42 data found, some of the data will be explained as a discussion of conversational implicature, namely, 10 general conversational implicature data; 8 custom conversational implicature data; and 4 scalable conversation implicature data, this was done because of time efficiency. The data is taken based on the differences and similarities in the implicature classification functions contained in the utterances of the sentences. This research also discussed the context related to the speech implicature of the conversation from the existing data

A. General Conversational Implicature

1. The implicature of conversation 1 can be seen through the utterance of 이게 더 빠르다 [This is faster] which is the answer to Athanasia's statement..

The implication was refusing to let Athanasia down from her arms. The father's answer was irrelevant to the question asked, if he was carried faster than walking alone because Athanasia had just recovered from her illness. Supposedly, the father can answer 'may' or 'may not'. From the father's answer, it can be assumed that the father did not want to let Athanasia go alone. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 1 is a general conversation implicature rejecting.

2. Conversational implicature 2 can be seen through the utterance of 지금보다 다섯 걸을 뒤에서 따라와라 [Follow me five steps

back from the current position] which is the answer to Felix's question.

The implication rejected Felix's suggestion to replace him carrying Athanasia, by ordering Felix to follow five steps behind him. The King's answer is irrelevant to the question asked, the King should be able to answer with 'yes' or 'no'. From the King's answer, it can be assumed that the King ordered Felix to step back and not let Felix carry Athanasia. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 2 is a commanding general conversation implicature.

3. Conversational implicature 3 can be seen through the utterance of 공부를 꼭 학자가 되려고만 하나? [Do people only study because they want to be scientists?] which was the answer to Lucas' question.

The implication is a rebuttal of the question asked by Lucas, by asking again. Seeing Athanasia studying from morning to evening made Lucas wonder by asking 'you want to be a scientist, right?'. Based on the dictionary a scientist is a person who has knowledge of a science, this is also synonymous with smart people, people who are experts in knowledge and people who like to learn. Athanasia's answer was irrelevant to the question Lucas asked, Athanasia should have been able to answer 'yes' or 'no'. From Athanasia's answer, it can be assumed that she did not study to become a scientist. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 3 is a general conversational implicature that argues.

B. Special Conversational Implicature

1. The conversational implicature of data 11 can be seen through the speech of 아티는 새로운 친구 필요 없어! 필릭스만 있으면 된다 말이야! [Athi doesn't need new friends! Athi is enough for Felix!] which is the answer to the question posed by Felix.

The implication is that he doesn't want or refuse to be friends with anyone so he prefers Felix as his friend. The true meaning of the utterance 'Athi is enough for Felix' is because Athanasia never interacted with anyone except the people in the palace so she had no intention of playing with anyone other than the Adjutant. Felix could understand the implicature in Athanasia's speech because he knew the context of the conversation that took place. Felix considered

Athanasia is too shy and afraid to make new friends. From Athanasia's answer, the interlocutor can interpret the meaning of the speech because he knows the context of the conversation. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 11 is a special conversation implicature rejecting.

2. The conversational implicature of data 12 can be seen through the speech of 공주님의 까망이는 오늘도 참 귀엽군요. 너무 조그마해서 한 입 거리도 안 되게 생겼네요.

[The Princess's Black, today is also very sweet. He's so small, it doesn't even feel like a mouthful] which is a statement made to answer Athanasia's real question for Felix.

The implication was to threaten Athanasia to keep quiet or Lucas would later eat Black (Athanasia's magical animal), if Athanasia intended to summon her father. From Lucas' statement Athanasia could understand because she knew the context of the conversation, because a few months ago Lucas really almost ate Black for food because Black is a magical animal and good for a witch to eat. Without knowing the context of the conversation, other people only interpret that Black is cute and small, and the utterance 'not up to one bite' is just a joke. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 12 is a specifically threatening conversation implicature.

3. The conversational implicature of data 13 can be seen through the utterances 그냥 적당히 맞먹어, 어차피 이제부터 같이 늙어 가는 처지에

[Similar to you. After all, from now on we will grow old together] which was the answer to Athanasia's question.

The implication is to tell that he is almost the same age as Athanasia, but the next statement 'after all, from now on we will grow old together' means that you don't have to ask too many questions because they will be friends forever. From Lucas' answer, the interlocutor could understand Lucas's intention as a report because he knew Lucas was a magician who could see the future and knew the context of the conversation. Without knowing the context of the conversation, people might misunderstand what Lucas meant. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 13 is a special conversation implicature reporting (telling).

4. The conversational implicature of data 14 can be seen from the utterance of 공주님의 어머니가 무희였던 것이 이럴 때는 도움이 되는군요 [It turns out that there is a benefit too, Mrs. Tuan Putri is a dancer] which is a speech statement made by the

teacher to Athanasia.

The implication is to subtly insinuate to Athanasia that Athanasia is great at dancing because her mother is a dancer. Even though if you know the context, Athanasia's mother had died since Athanasia was born. So, it is impossible for Athanasia's mother to make her master dance lessons because logically someone who is great at dancing is not genetically inherited. From the teacher's statement, Athanasia could understand the satire by answering 'I only study as taught by the teacher'. Without knowing the context of the conversation, people might misunderstand the meaning of the teacher's speech. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 14 is a special mock conversation implicature.

C. Scalable Conversational Implicature

1. Data implicature 19 can be seen through the speech of 전부 들으셨군요. 실은 혼자 울고 있을 것 같아서 찾기를 망설이고 있었습니다 [You hear everything. Actually, I was afraid to look for him because it looked like he was crying alone] which was the answer to the story proposed by Athanasia.

Through the word 전부 [jeonbu] which means 'all' where the speaker creates an implicature 'all'. In other words, the <all> scale and <all> scale are both the highest scales.

The implication was that Athanasia heard 'all' or 'all' of Ezekiel's mutterings. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 19 is a reporting (telling) scale conversation implicature.

2. The conversational implicature of data 20 can be seen through the utterances of 제가 곧 이곳을 떠나게 되거든요. 그래서 많이 서운한 것 같아요 [I will leave this place in a moment. Because of that it looks like he's sad a lot] which is the form of Ezekiel's statement to Athanasia. Through the word 많이 [manhi] which means 'a lot' where the speaker creates an implicature 'not a little', 'big enough'. In other words the <many> scale is a high scale.

The implication is that Zenith will be very saddened by the departure of her brother who will continue his education at the Atlanta academy and leave the Ezekiel house, and Athanasia agrees with that statement by answering 'she likes her brother very much'. Through this explanation, it can be concluded that data 20 is a conversational implicature of an agreeing scale.

CONCLUSION

Conversational implicature in this research is classified based on Yule's theory (2014) which is divided into three, namely, general conversational implicature; special conversational implicature; and scaled conversational implicature. Overall, 42 speech implicature data were found in the webtoon Suddenly, I Became a Princess episodes 21 to 41. It was found that 17 speech data contained general conversational implicature with 10 classification functions, namely: reject; Reign; argue; forbid; divert; confirm; approve; report (notify); deny; and scoffed. Meanwhile, there were 20 speech data containing special conversational implicatures with 8 classification functions, namely: reject; report (notify); threaten; mock; approve; confirm; hyperbole; and accuse. Furthermore, it was found that there were 5 speech data containing scaled conversational implicatures with 4 classification functions, namely: reporting (telling); approve; request; and confirmed.

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